

Condensation of *p*-Chloro- and *p*-Bromophenylacetic Acids with Aldehydes

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p-chloro- and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids have been condensed with a variety of aromatic aldehydes in presence of basic catalysts with the formation of substituted stilbenes.

In continuation of our previous work¹, we have now condensed phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids with some aldehydes. The purpose of this investigation is to study the influence of different substituents in the aromatic ring of both the components.

p-Chlorophenylacetic acid has been condensed with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, and 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde. The maximum yields of substituted stilbenes have been 57.4, 13.4, 81.4, 63.3 and 79.9% respectively, when piperidine was used as a catalyst and 53.7, 33.3, 0.0, 99.5 and 99.9% respectively when a mixture of pyridine (or triethylamine) and acetic anhydride was used as a catalyst. *p*-Bromophenylacetic acid has likewise been condensed with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde. Maximum yields obtained in these condensations are 55.4, 88.2, 94.7, 30.3, 0.0 and 6.2% respectively when piperidine was used as a catalyst and 16.5, 0.0, 0.0, 41.2, 24.0 and 26.5% respectively when a mixture of pyridine (or triethylamine) and acetic anhydride was used as a catalyst.

From the above results it can be concluded that the yields are higher with electron acceptor groups like NO₂, Cl on the aldehyde component and lower with electron releasing groups like OH, -NMe₂ etc, when the condensing agent is a mixture of pyridine (or triethylamine) and acetic anhydride. When, however, the condensing agent is piperidine, the results are just the opposite. The former observation is in line with the earlier results^{2,3}, but the latter is contrary to the generally accepted view (see however Pratt *et al*⁴). The failure of *p*-bromophenylacetic or *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid to condense with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde having electron releasing groups at the para position may be due to decreased reactivity of the aldehydes and self condensation of the acids resulting in the formation of polymeric substances, the nature of which has not been further investigated.

p-Substituted aldehydes are expected to be more reactive than *o*-substituted aldehydes, (steric hindrance) and this has been found to be the case. The maximum yields obtained in the condensation of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde with *p*-bromophenyl-

1. Vishnu Chandra and Srivastava, *this Journal*, 1966, 43, 433.
2. Ketcham and Jambothkar, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 1035.
3. Buckless, Bellis and Coder, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4972.
4. Preat and Werble, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 4638.

acetic acid in the presence of a mixture of acetic anhydride and base and base alone were found to be 41.2 and 30.3 and 24.0 and 0.00 respectively.

As chlorine has a greater affinity for electrons than bromine, *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid should be more reactive than *p*-bromophenylacetic acid. This has been found to be the case. The yields of the condensed products obtained in the reaction of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-chloro-benzaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, are 55.4, 88.2, 24.0, 41.2, 26.5 and 94.70 respectively. The yields of the corresponding products in the reaction of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid are 57.4, 90.2, 39.3, 54.7, 33.3 and 94.8% respectively¹.

p-Chlorophenylacetic acid has also been condensed with 5-bromo- and 3:5-dibromo salicylaldehyde. The yields are found to be greater than those obtained in the condensations with salicylaldehyde. Some other workers,^{5,6,7} have also reported that bromo-hydroxy-benzaldehydes were more reactive than *o*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde in similar condensation reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL

***p*-Chloro and *p*-Bromo-phenylacetic Acid:** *p*-Chlorophenylacetic acid was prepared from phenylacetic acid as reported earlier. *p*-Bromophenylacetic acid was prepared from phenylacetic acid through successive nitration, reduction, diazotisation, and Sandmeyer's bromination.

5-Bromosalicylaldehyde: 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde was prepared from salicylaldehyde by the method reported by Auwer's, Burger and Piria.⁸ 3:5 Dibromo

5. Lock and Bayer, *Ber.*, 1939, 72B, 1064.

6. Pandya and Singh, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 698.

7. Pandya, Rajani Bala Pandya and Singh, *This Journal*, 1952, 29, 363.

8. Buger and Piria, *Ber.* 1904, 37, 3934.

salicylaldehyde was prepared by bromination of salicylaldehyde (5 gm. of salicylaldehyde and 17.5 gm. of bromine). After each addition, the flask was vigorously shaken. The product which completely solidified in 3 days was filtered off and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 82-3°C.

Condensation of p-Chlorophenylacetic acid with Aromatic aldehydes:

With p-nitrobenzaldehyde: Equimolecular quantities of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid (0.17 gm), aldehyde (0.15 gm.) and traces of base were heated in a flask fitted with reflux condenser, at different temperatures *viz.*, 100, 120 and 140°C for different periods *i.e.*, 6, 12 and 18 hours in the presence, of different bases *viz.*, pyridine, piperidine, α -picoline, pyridine and acetic anhydride, triethylamine and acetic anhydride. The resulting mass in each case was treated with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate and the solution filtered. The residue was recrystallised from ethanol and found to be 4-chloro-4'-nitrostilbene on the basis of its m.p. 183-4°C (reported⁹ 184°C) (Found: Cl, 13.5, C₁₄H₁₀ClNO₂ requires Cl 13.65%). The filtrate was neutralised with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acid so precipitated was recrystallised from ethanol. This was found to be α -carboxy-4'-chloro-4'-nitro-stilbene, m.p. 171-2°C (Found: Cl, 11.4. equiv. 303.5 C₁₅H₁₀ClNO₄ requires, Cl, 11.6, equiv., 303.5) Maximum yield of 55.4%, of the stilbene was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 6 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine (2 drops). A maximum yield of 53.7% of the acid was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of triethylamine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops). Acid was the only product when a mixture of triethylamine (or pyridine) and acetic anhydride was used as catalyst and the stilbene was the only product when piperidine and α -picoline were used as catalysts.

With p-chlorobenzaldehyde: The acid obtained was found to be 4:4' dichloro- α - β -diphenylacrylic acid, m.p. 152-3°C (reported¹⁰ 152-3°C), (Found: Cl, 24.05, equiv., 293.1 C₁₇H₁₀Cl₂O₂ requires Cl, 24.17. equiv. 293. Maximum yield of 33.3% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of triethylamine and acetic anhydride. Maximum yield of 13.4% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine.

With p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde: The stilbene obtained was found to be 4-chloro-4' hydroxy stilbene, m.p. 182°C (reported¹¹ m.p. 182°C), (Found: Cl, 15.6, C₁₄H₁₁ClO requires Cl, 15.3%). No acid product was isolated from the filtrate. Maximum yield of 61.4% of stilbene was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine.

With 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde: The product was found to be 6-bromo-3-(*p*-chlorophenyl)coumarin, m.p. 220°C, (Found: Br, 23.70, Cl, 10.7. C₁₅H₉ClBrO₂ requires 23.80, Cl, 10.6%). Maximum yields of 69.5% and 63.3% of the condensed product were obtained when the reactants were heated at 150°C and 120°C for 6 hours and 12 hours in the presence of a mixture of pyridine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops) and piperidine respectively.

With 3:5-Dibromo-salicylaldehyde: The product was found to be 6:8-dibromo-3-

9. Dale and Charles, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 76, 2259.

10. Weeler and Padon, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 1473.

11. Cavallin and Massarani, *Maggioni and C. Società Per Azioni, U.S.* 1939, 2, 378,

(*p*-chlorophenyl)coumarin, m.p. 247-9°C, (Found: Cl, 8.30, Br, 38.5, C₁₅H₇ClBr₂O₂ requires Cl, 8.56, Br, 38.6%). Maximum yields of the condensed product were obtained when the reactants were heated at 150°C and 120°C for 6 hours in the presence of traces of pyridine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops) and piperidine respectively.

Condensation of p-Bromophenylacetic Acid with Aldehydes:

With Benzaldehyde: The acid obtained was found to be α -carboxy-4-bromostilbene, m.p. 190°C (reported¹² m.p. 196°C) (Found: Br, 26.7%, equiv., 302.9, C₁₅H₁₁BrO₂ requires Br, 26.03%, equiv., 303). Maximum yields of 55.4% and 18.5% were obtained when the reactants were heated at 110°C and 100°C for 6 hours and 19 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine and a mixture of triethylamine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops) respectively.

With Anisaldehyde: The product was found to be α -carboxy-4-bromo-4'-methoxy stilbene, m.p. 224-25°C, (Found: Br, 352.8 24.02 equiv. (C₁₆H₁₃BrO₂ requires Br, 23.98, equiv. 333.10). Maximum yield of 88.2% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated in the presence of traces of piperidine at 120°C for 12 hours.

With O-Nitrobenzaldehyde: The product was found to be α -carboxy-4-bromo-2-nitrostilbene, m.p. 168-70°C (reported¹³, m.p. 169-70°) (Found, Br, 22.1%, equiv. 347.9 C₁₅H₁₀BrNO₄ requires, Br, 22.9%, equiv., 348.2). Maximum yield of 24.0% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140-5°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of pyridine and acetic anhydride.

With p-Nitrobenzaldehyde: The same procedure was followed as in the condensation of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde. The acid so obtained was recrystallised from ethanol and was found to be α -carboxy-4-bromo-4'-nitro stilbene, m.p. 184-5°C, (Found: Br, 22.3%, equiv. 347, C₁₅H₁₀BrNO₄ requires Br, 22.9%, equiv. 348) The residue which was neutral, was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and was found to be 4-bromo-4'-nitro stilbene, m.p. 202°C (reported¹⁴, m.p. 201°C), (Found: Br, 25.9%, C₁₄H₁₀BrNO₂ requires Br, 26.3%). Maximum yield of 30.3% of the stilbene was obtained when the reactants were heated at 120°C for 6 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine and a maximum yield of 41.2% of the acid was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of a mixture of triethylamine and acetic anhydride. Acid was the only product when a mixture of triethylamine (or pyridine) and acetic anhydride was used as a catalyst and stilbene was the only product when piperidine α -picoline were used as catalysts.

With p-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde: The product obtained was found to be 4-bromo-4'-dimethylaminostilbene, m.p. 231-2°C (reported¹⁵ m.p. 231-2°C), (Found: Br, 26.2%, C₁₆H₁₆BrN requires Br, 26.4%). Maximum yield of 94.0% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 120°C for 12 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine.

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13. May and Moscittig, *J. Org Chem*, 1946, 11, 627.

14. Feurer, Turcotte, Giguere, Roberge, *Can. J. Res.* 1948, 26B, 70.

15. Tadros and Latif, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3823,

With p-Chlorobenzaldehyde: The acid obtained was found to be 4-bromo- α -carboxy-4'-chloro-stilbene, m.p. 236°C, (Found: Cl, 10.3%, Br, 23.0; equiv 336.7. $C_{15}H_{10}BrClO_2$ requires Cl, 10.4%, Br, 23.3%; equiv. 338). Maximum yields of 26.5% and 6.2% of the condensed product were obtained when the reactants were heated at 150°C and 120°C for 6 hours in the presence of traces of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride, and piperidine respectively.

Condensation of Phenylacetic acid with p-Chlorobenzaldehyde: The acid obtained was found to be 4-chloro- α : β -diphenylacrylic acid, m.p. 200-3°C (reported¹⁶, m.p. 201-3°C), (Found: Cl, 10.35, equiv., 258.7. $C_{15}H_{11}ClO_2$ requires Cl, 10.37% equiv., 258.7.) Maximum yield of 28.6% of the acid was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140°C for 6 hours in the presence of traces of piperidine.

Thanks of authors are due to Professor R. P. Rastogi, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, for allowing necessary facilities.

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Received January 15, 1966.